

Breeding for thermotolerance in dairy cattle: Production versus fertility traits

M. J. Carabaño,^{1*} C. Díaz,¹ and M. Ramón^{1,2}

¹Department of Animal Breeding and Genetics, National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA-CSIC), 28040 Madrid, Spain

²Regional Center for Animal Selection and Reproduction (CERSYRA), Regional Institute for Research and Development in Agriculture and Forestry (IRIAF-JCCM), 13300 Valdepeñas, Spain

ABSTRACT

The decline in production of milk and its components has been extensively studied as an indicator of heat tolerance for genetic evaluations. However, the antagonistic relationship between high production and functionality raises questions about the suitability of using productive traits as indicators of heat tolerance. This study aimed to estimate changes in the relationship between production and fertility under thermoneutral (TN) and heat stress (HS) conditions, to define breeding strategies that enhance adaptation to high heat loads while maintaining both productivity and functionality. The analyzed dataset included records on 100,467 Holstein cows of first-lactation milk, fat, and protein yields (703,574 records for each yield) and conception rate (CR) at first insemination in first lactation of 247,378 cows in Spain. Temperature-humidity indices averaged over the day of milk recording or day of artificial insemination and the 2 previous days for milk traits, or the subsequent 7 d for fertility, were used to measure the heat load associated with each record. Bicharacter sire models were employed, incorporating one of the yield traits and the fertility trait. Models included random regressions with Legendre polynomials for production traits and a broken-line function for fertility to describe the trait responses to increasing heat loads. This approach allowed for the estimation of trait levels under TN and HS conditions, the slope of response under HS as heat tolerance indicators, and the correlations among these variables. The 3 yield traits exhibited estimated negative genetic correlations between their level under TN conditions and their slopes of response under HS, ranging from -0.38 for fat yield to -0.59 for milk yield. For CR, this correlation was close to zero. Estimated genetic correlations between yield traits under TN conditions and the decline in CR under HS were nearly null, ranging from -0.06 for fat yield to 0.07 for

protein yield. This suggests that cows with higher production potential under TN conditions are not necessarily more susceptible to fertility decline under HS. Conversely, the correlations between fertility potential under TN conditions and the slopes of production decline under HS were positive, ranging from 0.34 for protein yield to 0.51 for fat yield. This indicates that cows with lower production losses under HS tend to have better fertility performance under TN conditions. Furthermore, the correlations between heat tolerance based on production and fertility declines under HS were positive, ranging from 0.22 for fat yield to 0.65 for milk yield. This suggests that a significant proportion of animals have the potential to maintain both productive and fertility levels under HS. Finally, the genetic correlation between fertility and production traits improved as heat load increased. For milk yield, this correlation shifted from -0.30 under TN to nearly null under extreme heat conditions. Reaction to heat load in functional traits such as fertility should help in selecting animals that show high levels of production under HS due to a better adaptation to hot conditions driven by functional reasons.

Key words: heat tolerance, milk yield, fertility, trade-off production-fertility

INTRODUCTION

The heat tolerance (HT) of dairy animals has always been a concern in warm regions of the world and is increasingly gaining attention in traditionally temperate areas due to climate change. Although the impact of heat stress (HS) on animals is being mitigated through various strategies, such as modifications in barn conditions, management practices, or feeding (e.g., Osei-Amponsah et al., 2019, for a review), long-term adaptation through selective breeding may help optimize dairy production in rising temperatures. Consequently, selecting heat-tolerant animals is becoming a key focus for the dairy industry, as highly selected dairy cows are the most affected by HS (West, 2003). Although there is no single definition to HT, it can be understood as an

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*Corresponding author: mjc@inia.csic.es

The list of standard abbreviations for JDS is available at adsa.org/jds-abbreviations-25. Nonstandard abbreviations are available in the Notes.

animal's ability to thermoregulate effectively enough to maintain production, reproduction, and overall health under HS conditions.

Because production (mainly protein yield) is the primary economic driver of dairy farms, is easier to measure, and has a higher heritability than fertility, selecting animals that are able to maintain their productive level under HS is an appealing strategy. In dairy production, the most common approach for selecting heat-tolerant animals involves using milk recording data along with meteorological information to characterize and quantify heat load (HL), allowing for the estimation of individual production losses under HS. Animals with the smallest production losses under HS are the primary selection targets. There is broad agreement (e.g., the recent review by Habimana et al., 2023) on using reaction norm models (either broken-line or polynomial functions) to estimate HT. Individual slopes of change in production under HS derived from these models are used as indicators of HT. Estimated genetic values for HT show variability in all studied populations. In several countries, genetic evaluations are already available or are in preparation (Nguyen et al., 2017; Finocchiaro et al., 2022; McWhorter et al., 2023). Measuring HT based on production losses under HS (HT-P) has the advantage of leveraging large amounts of production data from milk recording schemes covering a wide range of HL conditions. The only additional requirement is integrating meteorological data from nearby weather stations to conduct genetic evaluations using existing methods and software. However, using HT-P as a selection criterion presents some challenges. One key drawback is the antagonistic relationship between high production and HT-P observed in many studies. High-producing animals tend to experience greater production declines under HS, whereas lower-producing animals show smaller decline (e.g., Cartwright et al., 2023).

Alternatively, although to a much lesser extent compared with declines in production, HT based on fertility loss under HS (HT-F) has also been considered (Ravagnolo et al., 2002; Oseni et al., 2004; Pszczola et al., 2009; Biffani et al., 2016). Fertility is greatly affected by HS in all its stages, ovulation, spermatogenesis, conception, and gestation (Wolfenson and Roth, 2019) and could be a better indicator of adaptation to high temperatures than HT-P from a functional point of view. Moreover, maintaining year-round calving is economically beneficial for dairy farms, ensuring a steady milk supply. Fertility data are commonly recorded in national breeding programs and could be readily used for HT evaluations. However, fertility is largely influenced by uncontrolled nongenetic factors and shows low heritability. Another limitation of HT-F is the variability in fertility measures across national breeding schemes, as different indicators, such as days open, nonreturn rates (NRR), and conception rate

(CR), capture distinct components of fertility. Results of artificial inseminations (AI), though not always available, provide the most direct measure of a cow's ability to conceive and are the most reliable for assessing the influence of environmental conditions such as HS on CR. Previous studies on the genetic basis of HT-F have focused on days open (Oseni et al., 2004; Pszczola et al., 2009) and NRR (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2002; Biffani et al., 2016). However, the relationship between HT-P and HT-F has received little attention. Ravagnolo and Misztal (2002) reported a near-zero genetic correlation between HT-P and HT-F (measured as NRR), whereas more recent findings by Vinet et al. (2024) suggest a small but positive correlation between these traits when using CR as the fertility measure.

Overall, both HT-P and HT-F present advantages and disadvantages for the genetic selection of heat-tolerant animals in national breeding programs. Understanding the genetic relationships between production and reproductive responses to increased HL is crucial before integrating these traits into selection programs. To do so, we will deep into the relationship between both traits under different environmental constraints that go from no-constraint or comfort (thermoneutrality) to more acute thermal stress. This study aimed to estimate the genetic correlations between production and fertility (measured as CR) under thermoneutral (TN) and HS conditions, considering both general levels and HT indicators. Investigating these relationships will help define more effective breeding strategies to enhance animal adaptation to high HL while maintaining both productive and functional performance. We hypothesize that both HT-P and HT-F may be necessary for improving long-term adaptation to HS.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data

Phenotypes and Pedigree. The Spanish Holstein-Friesian breed association (CONAFE) provided production and fertility data, along with pedigree information, used in this analysis. To allow for data spanning across several generations, production and fertility data recorded along a 21-yr period (2000–2020) were requested from CONAFE. The production data used were first-lactation milk, fat, and protein yields on the day of the official monthly milk recording. These data were filtered to eliminate outliers (data beyond the upper and lower 0.1 percentile distribution for milk, fat, and protein yields) and records from less/more than 20/305 d in lactation. The fertility data provided consisted of calving and AI events from the reproductive recording. From that information, CR (0 = AI failure, 1 = AI success) was obtained

following the rules of the golden standard for fertility of EuroGenomics (2022). For computational purposes, CR data were limited to results of the first insemination of cows in the first lactation.

Meteorological Information. Daily maximum, minimum, and average temperatures, along with relative humidity, were obtained from the Spanish National Meteorological Agency (AEMET) for the same period as the productive data. Meteorological data were sourced from the weather stations closest to each herd on the respective dates of production or fertility recording. A daily temperature-humidity index (THI) was calculated using the commonly applied formula for dairy cattle (NRC, 1971):

$$\text{THI} = (1.8 \times T + 32) - (0.55 - 0.55 \times \text{RH}) \times [(1.8 \times T + 32) - 58],$$

where T ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) represents the daily average temperature and RH (%) is the daily average relative humidity. Daily averages were chosen over maximum values because previous studies on this population indicated that average daily temperatures improved goodness of fit of the response to HS compared with maximum values (Carabaño et al., 2014). To assess HL for milk, fat, and protein yields, the mean of daily average THI on the test-day of recording and the 2 previous days (THI_Y) were used to characterize the HL of animals, to account for lag effects. For CR data, the mean of daily average of THI values on the AI date and the subsequent 7 d (THI_{CR}) were computed as a measure of the HL. This choice derived from previous results showing that HL on the post AI period seems to be more relevant than HL previous to the AI date (Morton et al., 2007).

Combined Meteorological and Production or Fertility Datasets. The productive and fertility datasets were combined with their corresponding THI values. The combined dataset was also edited before analyses. Records were excluded if they lacked associated THI data or if the nearest available weather station was more than 20 km from the farm. In the final datasets, the average ($\pm\text{SD}$) distance from herds to the closest weather station was 8.4 (± 3.4) km. Additionally, cows or sires were required to have information obtained under HS. Average or population HS thresholds for yields ($\text{THI}_Y^o = 72$) and CR ($\text{THI}_{\text{CR}}^o = 66$) have been previously established for this population in Mattalia et al. (2023). To include individual animals that might have a lower threshold than the average value, and given that the proportion of records above the HS thresholds was relatively small, we used as cut-off points to discard animals with THI values that were a little below the population thresholds. Thus, for production traits, cows without any yield records with an associated $\text{THI}_Y > 68$ and fewer than

3 test-day records were removed. For the CR dataset, because each cow had only one record, the requirement was that sires of cows must have at least one daughter with CR measured under $\text{THI}_{\text{CR}} > 63$. Finally, both datasets were further refined by excluding records from sires with fewer than 20 daughters across at least 10 herds, as well as records from contemporary groups (defined as herd-year of calving) with fewer than 5 observations.

After all edits, the production data included 703,574 test-day records of first-lactation milk, fat, and protein yields per day, recorded in the official test-day in 100,467 Holstein cows. Fertility data consisted of CR records of first AI in first lactation of 247,378 cows. In total, 76,903 cows had both fertility and productive records. Cows with productive records were sired by 2,036 bulls, and 1,166 sires had both fertility and productive data. The pedigree file consisted of 2,547 bulls tracing back 3 generations.

Statistical Analyses

Production and fertility data were analyzed together by running 3 bicharacter sire models. Each model included one of the yield traits (milk, fat, or protein yield) and the fertility trait. Provided the differences in computational requirements, we first decided between the use of sire or animal model. Thus, an animal model was first applied to CR, but convergence of the sampling chains was poor. For this trait, where only one measure per animal is available, fitting a trajectory along a range of values for the HL mostly relies on the pedigree information. In a trait such as CR, with low heritability, estimates of individual animal reaction to changes in thermal load using an animal model may be inaccurate. In contrast, sires have many daughters performing in a range of environmental conditions, allowing for a good appraisal of the reaction of a genotype to changes in THI, which justified the use of the bicharacter sire models in the subsequent analyses.

The statistical model equation for production traits within the bicharacter model was

$$y_{ijkscr}^Y = \text{HY}_i^Y + \text{AC}_j^Y + \text{DIM}_k + \sum_{l=1}^3 b_l x_l + \sum_{m=0}^2 \alpha_{m_s}^Y x_m + \sum_{m=0}^2 \omega_{m_c}^Y x_m + e_{ijkscr}^Y, \quad [1]$$

where y_{ijkscr}^Y represents the daily yield on the milk recording date ($Y = \text{milk, fat, or protein yield}$); HY_i^Y accounts for the effect of the i th herd and year of calving on yield; AC_j^Y represents the j th class of age at calving (11 classes) on yield; DIM_k corresponds to the k th class of DIM (11 classes); x_1 and x_m are covariates for the quadratic Legen-

Table 1. Number of data (N) and summary statistics (mean, SD, minimum [Min], maximum [Max], and percentiles [P.]) for the analyzed traits and heat load variables

Item ¹	N	Mean	SD	Min	P.10	P.30	P.50	P.70	P.90	Max
CR (0/1)	247,378	0.45	0.50	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
Milk (kg)	703,574	33.62	6.74	12.2	25.0	30.0	33.5	37.1	42.4	58.5
Fat (kg)	703,574	1.21	0.30	0.5	0.85	1.04	1.18	1.33	1.59	2.47
Protein (kg)	703,574	1.09	0.21	0.51	0.82	0.98	1.09	1.20	1.37	1.74
THI _Y	53,310	57.64	8.98	40.00	45.92	51.60	57.20	63.24	69.94	79.30
THI _{CR}	125,556	56.29	8.15	34.54	45.70	50.95	56.24	61.73	66.82	76.84

¹CR = conception rate (0 = failure, 1 = success); THI_Y = temperature-humidity index averaged over the day of milk recording and the 2 previous days; THI_{CR} = temperature-humidity index averaged over the insemination date and the subsequent 7 d.

dre polynomials for the THI_Y corresponding to the observed value of the trait, rescaled to the interval [-1, 1] for the average and individual response curves, respectively; b_1 , $\alpha_{m_s}^Y$, and $\omega_{m_c}^Y$ are regression coefficients defining the average, sire additive genetic, and cow permanent environmental curve of response in the trait to changes in THI, respectively; and $e_{ijk_{sr}}$ is the residual term. Notice that $\sum_{m=0}^2 \alpha_{m_s}^Y x_m$ is the genetic component of the response of the trait at a given THI value, representing the predicted genetic level of the trait for sire s at that THI value. Moreover, the intercept for the individual response curve is the sire additive genetic value of the trait when x equals 0, which occurs when THI_Y equals the mean value of THI_Y (THI_Y = 57.64), which is within the TN region. Therefore, the value of the intercept, $\alpha_{0_s}^Y$, represents the genetic level of the trait for sire s under thermoneutrality.

In Equation [1], class effects for AC_j and DIM_k and regression coefficients for the average response to TLs (b_1) were considered as systematic (fixed) effects whereas the HY_i effect and the additive genetic and permanent environmental regression coefficients were treated as random effects with associated variances, $\text{var}(HY_i^Y) = \sigma_{hy}^2$ for all i and $\text{covar}(HY_i^Y, HY_{i'}^Y) = 0$ for $i \neq i'$; $\text{var}(\alpha_{m_s}^Y) = \sigma_{\alpha_m}^2$ for $m=0, \dots, 2$; $\text{covar}(\alpha_{m_s}^Y, \alpha_{m'_s}^Y) = \sigma_{\alpha_m, \alpha_{m'}}^2$ for $m \neq m'$; $\text{var}(\omega_{m_c}^Y) = \sigma_{\omega_m}^2$ for $m = 0, \dots, 2$; $\text{covar}(\omega_{m_c}^Y, \omega_{m'_c}^Y) = \sigma_{\omega_m, \omega_{m'}}^2$ for $m \neq m'$; and $\text{var}(e) = \sigma_e^2$. Levels of these random effects were assumed to be uncorrelated across effects.

For fertility, the so-called “broken-line” model was used. This model assumes no response to increased HL within the TN zone and a linear response beyond a certain threshold. The smaller amount of information available for CR compared with the production traits, together with the facts that CR has a low heritability (implying that more information is needed to get reliable estimates of genetic values) and that, in our experi-

ence, the slopes are less accurately estimated than the genetic level of the traits, justifies the use of a simpler model compared with the use of polynomials for this trait. The broken-line model relies only on 2 parameters, intercept and slope of change under HS, and 3 corresponding (co)variances, which already represent our target parameters.

The model equation for fertility was

$$y_{ijk_{sr}}^{CR} = HY_i^{CR} + AC_j^{CR} + VWP_k + b(\text{THI}_{CR} - \text{THI}_{CR}^o) + \alpha_{0_s}^{CR} + \alpha_{1_s}^{CR}(\text{THI}_{CR} - \text{THI}_{CR}^o) + e_{ijk_{sr}}, \quad [2]$$

where $y_{ijk_{sr}}^{CR}$ represents the binary value for CR at the first insemination in the first lactation; HY_i^{CR} is the effect of the i th herd and year of insemination for CR; AC_j^{CR} is the j th class of age at calving (11 classes) for CR; VWP is the effect of the voluntary waiting period (interval from calving to first AI, 5 classes); b is a regression coefficient; THI_{CR} was the THI for CR; THI_{CR}^o is the HS threshold for fertility in this population; $\alpha_{0_s}^{CR}$ is the intercept, representing the additive genetic sire effect for fertility under TN conditions (i.e., below the HS threshold); $\alpha_{1_s}^{CR}$ is the additive genetic sire effect for the linear regression coefficient of response to THI_{CR} beyond the HS threshold; and $e_{ijk_{sr}}$ is the residual term.

In Equation [2], class effects for AC and VWP and the regression coefficients for the average response to thermal loads (b) was considered as a systematic (fixed) effect, whereas the HY effect and the additive genetic and permanent environmental regression coefficients were treated as random effects with associated variances, $\text{var}(HY^{CR}) = \sigma_h^2$, $\text{var}(\alpha_0^{CR}) = \sigma_{\alpha_0}^2$, $\text{var}(\alpha_1^{CR}) = \sigma_{\alpha_1}^2$, $\text{covar}(\alpha_0^{CR}, \alpha_1^{CR}) = \sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_1}^2$, and $\text{var}(e) = \sigma_e^2$.

Random regression coefficients for sire additive genetic effects and residual effects were assumed to be correlated between production and fertility traits. A

precise description of the (co)variance structure for the random effects in the previous models can be found in the Appendix.

Solutions for random regression coefficients for sire additive genetic effects in models [1] $(\alpha_{m_s}^Y)$ and [2] $(\alpha_{0_s}^{CR}, \alpha_{1_s}^{CR})$ were used to estimate target parameters: (1) individual genetic level for a trait along the THI scale and (2) slopes of change in genetic value under HS, as indicators of heat tolerance from production (HT-P) or fertility (HT-F). From the estimated (co)variances for random regression coefficients within and across traits, genetic correlations involving levels and slopes, both within and between production and fertility traits, were evaluated under TN versus HS conditions. The THI values for TN/HS conditions were those below/above the HS threshold for each trait ($THI_Y^o = 72$ for yields and $THI_{CR}^o = 66$ for CR, as previously mentioned). The THI values corresponding to TN conditions were set at $THI = 55$ (a value in the center of the TN region for production traits) and $THI < 66$ for production and fertility, respectively. For HS, 2 values of THI, aiming at representing mild and severe HS, $THI_Y = 72$ and 77 for productive traits, and $THI_{CR} = 69$ and 74 for the fertility trait, respectively, were considered. The formulas used to estimate levels and slopes together with variances, heritabilities, and correlations between those parameters at different values of the THI are described in the Appendix.

Solutions for position (fixed effects and random regression coefficients) and dispersion parameters (covariances for the random regressions coefficients within and between traits) in the bivariate models were obtained using the BLUPF90 family of programs (Miszta et al., 2018), specifically through a Bayesian approach implemented in the GIBBSF90+ program. A single Markov chain of 100,000 samples were generated, with a conservative burn-in period of 20,000 iterations and a thinning interval of 10 for each variance component. The convergence was visually determined by plotting the Gibbs samples, as well as by using the coda package (Plummer et al., 2006). Features of the posterior distributions for the parameters of interest (heritabilities and correlations) were obtained from the samples of the posterior distribution of the (co)variance components associated with the bivariate models analyzed. Estimates of parameters of interest were obtained from their posterior means. In addition, 95% high density probability intervals (95HPD) and probability of correlations being different from 0 were calculated. This probability was obtained by calculating the proportion of samples above or below zero given that the posterior means were positive or negative, respectively.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the number of records and summary statistics for milk, fat, and protein daily yields, respectively, and fertility, as well as HL variables. Average values for production traits were 33.62, 1.21, and 1.09 kg/d for milk, fat, and protein daily yields, respectively, and the average CR for first insemination for first-lactation cows was 45%. The THI values for yield traits (mean of daily average THI values for 3 d) ranged from 40.0 to 79.3, whereas the THI values for CR (mean of daily average THI values for 8 d) ranged from 34.54 to 76.84, showing different scales. Histograms illustrating the distribution of records across THI values for yield traits and CR are shown in Figure 1. Taking into account the HS thresholds determined for this population for production and CR (Mattalia et al., 2023), around 8% of the milk production records (circa 56,300) and 10% of the CR records (circa 24,700), were recorded under HS.

Within-Trait Results

Figure 2 displays the estimated heritability and 95HPD intervals across the THI range for yield traits and CR. Heritability estimates declined steadily for fat and protein yields, whereas for milk yield, they initially increased until reaching a peak at approximately $THI_Y = 60$, after which they began to decrease. On the contrary, heritability estimates for CR showed larger values as THI_{CR} increased beyond the HS threshold ($THI_{CR} = 66$) for this trait. Heterogeneous heritabilities due to environmental changes can be an indication of genotype-by-environment (GxE) interaction. To explore this further, we estimated the genetic correlation between trait values across the environmental gradient, represented by THI. Estimated correlations, in Figure 3, showed values above 0.8 for all yield traits, indicative of no relevant GxE interaction. In contrast, the estimated genetic correlations between CR level under different THI_{CR} values were around 0.7 when comparing the extremes of the THI_{CR} gradient (i.e., the lower [35] and largest [77] values of THI_{CR}). This suggests a more significant GxE interaction for CR than for yield traits.

Table 2 shows a summary of the correlations between slopes under heat stress and levels under both TN and HS conditions for yield traits and for CR. The 3 yield traits showed the same pattern, with estimated negative correlations between level of the trait and slopes of response under HS. These estimated correlations were less antagonistic for level of the trait under HS ($THI_Y = 72$ or 77) than for the trait level under TN ($THI_Y = 55$) conditions. For example, for milk yield, estimated correlations between slope at $THI_Y = 72$, and level of the trait at $THI_Y = 55/72/77$ were $-0.58/-0.38/-0.25$. Somehow

Figure 1. Histograms for count of records in 2 degree bins of the temperature-humidity index for yield (THI_Y) and conception rate (THI_{CR}). The THI values for yields are daily THI means averaged over the day of milk recording and the 2 previous days, whereas THI values for CR are daily THI means averaged over the day of insemination and the 7 subsequent days.

unexpectedly, correlations between levels and slopes under HS showed similar or slightly more antagonistic values for the mild (THI_Y = 72) versus the more severe HS (THI_Y = 77). For example, correlations between level under TN and slopes under the 2 HS values of THI_Y were -0.58 versus -0.59 , -0.44 versus -0.40 , and -0.41 versus -0.38 for milk, fat, and protein yields, respectively.

For CR, estimated correlations between its level under TN conditions and the linear regression coefficient describing CR response beyond the HS threshold were small and slightly negative, ranging from 0.01 when analyzed jointly with milk yield to -0.03 when analyzed with protein yield. This suggests that cows with higher or lower CR under TN conditions are not necessarily more or less susceptible to HS, respectively. Furthermore, the

correlation between CR reaction slope under HS and its level under HS was positive, indicating a synergistic relationship between genetic potential for fertility under HS and HT-F.

Relationship Between Fertility and Productive Traits

Table 3 presents the characteristics of the posterior distribution of genetic correlations between levels under TN or HS conditions and slopes of response under HS between CR and each of the yield traits. For correlations between levels of the traits under TN conditions, the estimated values were negative for all 3 productive traits. This indicates an antagonistic relationship between high productive levels and CR under TN conditions. The es-

Figure 2. Posterior mean (PM; points) and 95% high probability density interval (bars) of the posterior distribution of heritabilities for yields and conception rate (CR) along increasing values of the temperature-humidity index (THI). The THI values for yields are daily THI means averaged over the day of milk recording and the 2 previous days, whereas THI values for CR are daily THI means averaged over the day of insemination and the 7 subsequent days.

timated genetic correlations between the level of yield traits under TN conditions and slope of decline in CR under HS were close to null, ranging from -0.10 for fat yield to 0.01 for protein yield. This suggests that cows with higher production potential under TN conditions are not expected to experience greater fertility declines under HS. Conversely, the estimated correlations between the ability to conceive via AI under TN conditions (intercept for CR) and the slopes of production decline under HS were positive, ranging from 0.34 for protein yield at $\text{THI}_Y = 72$ to 0.50 or 0.51 for fat yield at $\text{THI}_Y = 77$ and $\text{THI}_Y = 72$, respectively. This indicates that cows with higher fertility levels under TN conditions will tend to show lower production losses under HS. For correlations under HS, the genetic level for both production and fertility under HS were positively correlated with the slope of reaction to HS of the other type of trait, fertility and production, respectively. The estimated correlations were smaller for level of production versus slope of reaction in fertility under HS. Values ranged from 0.09 for the correlation between fat level at $\text{THI}_Y = 72$ to 0.34 for the correlation between protein level at $\text{THI}_Y = 77$ and slope of reaction in CR, respectively. For estimated correlations between level of CR under HS and slopes of reaction to HS in productive traits, the range

was broader, from 0.48 for level of CR at moderate HS ($\text{THI}_{CR} = 69$) and protein yield under also moderate HS ($\text{THI}_Y = 72$) to 0.70 for level of CR at more severe HS ($\text{THI}_{CR} = 74$) and milk yield under moderate HS ($\text{THI}_Y = 72$). Finally, still following the results shown in Table 3, the estimated correlation between heat tolerance indicators (slopes of reaction) from production (HT-P) or from fertility (HT-F) decays under HS were positive, ranging from 0.22 for fat production under $\text{THI}_Y = 77$ to 0.65 for milk yield under $\text{THI}_Y = 72$.

Estimates of changes in correlations between fertility and production under different HL can provide valuable insights into how climate change may affect the antagonistic relationship between these 2 traits. Figure 4 illustrates changes in estimated correlations under progressively higher HL scenarios. Since, as previously mentioned, THI_Y and THI_{CR} are on different scales—due to THI_Y being averaged over a shorter period than THI_{CR} —we selected equivalent values for the 2 THI to ensure comparability. The equivalence between THI values for fertility and production was approximated comparing the distribution of values for each index that appears in Table 1. For the HS part, the 2 indices differ in, approximately, 3 units. For all productive traits, the estimated genetic correlation between fertility and production increased as HL intensified. Notably, milk yield, which had the most negative correlation with fertility under TN conditions, showed a near-null antagonism under the most extreme heat scenario. Although the large variance in the posterior distribution of these correlations suggests that differences across THI values may not be very relevant, our findings indicate that increasing HL in future climate change scenarios are unlikely to further deteriorate the relationship between milk production traits and fertility measured as CR.

DISCUSSION

Fertility and production are 2 physiological functions significantly affected by HS. However, the impact on the genetic component of the response to high HL differed. In this study, production traits exhibited a decrease in genetic variability—and consequently, in heritability—as the THI increased. Additionally, strong genetic correlations were observed between production levels under high HL and TN conditions, along with antagonistic relationships between production level and reaction slope under HS. A reduction in genetic variance under more restrictive environments is considered a sign of G×E interaction, as the genetic potential of highly productive animals is expected to be constrained. Heat stress likely exacerbates this effect by worsening the negative energy balance of high-producing animals (Baumgard and Rhoads, 2012). Other studies have also reported reduced genetic vari-

Figure 3. Contour plots of the posterior means of the additive genetic correlations between yields (Y, first row) and between conception rates (CR, second row) along the temperature-humidity index (THI) values associated with heat stress. The THI values for yields are daily THI means averaged over the day of milk recording and the 2 previous days, whereas THI values for CR are daily THI means averaged over the day of insemination and the 7 subsequent days. For CR, each contour plot corresponds to estimated correlations obtained from the bivariate analyses for one yield trait and CR.

ability and heritability for production traits under HS (Brügemann et al., 2011; Hammami et al., 2015). However, increased genetic variability under high HL has been observed in other works (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2000; Bernabucci et al., 2014). Despite variance heterogeneity, estimates of genetic correlations between genetic values at distant THI levels exceeded the generally accepted 0.8 threshold for G×E interaction (Robertson, 1959). Similar results have been found in previous studies, with genetic correlations above 0.8 between production levels under HS and non-HS conditions (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2000; Brügemann et al., 2011; Bernabucci et al., 2014; Carabaño et al., 2014; Hammami et al., 2015; Vinet et al., 2024). The observed variance heterogeneity and correlations along the environmental scale suggest that highly productive animals remain highly ranked under HS, though with a reduced performance gap compared with intermediate or lower producers. Finally, the antagonistic

genetic relationship between production level and rate of decline under HS indicates that higher-producing animals tend to be less heat tolerant. This finding aligns with results from numerous other studies (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2000; Brügemann et al., 2011; Bernabucci et al., 2014; Carabaño et al., 2014; Hammami et al., 2015; Vinet et al., 2024).

For fertility, measured as CR, estimated genetic variance increased under high HL. A more pronounced G×E interaction was observed between HS and TN conditions, and an estimated genetic correlation close to zero between fertility potential under TN conditions and the slope of change under HS. Higher variability of fertility performance under HS has been consistently reported in other studies on dairy cattle populations (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2002; Brügemann et al., 2011; Biffani et al., 2016; Ansari-Mahyari et al., 2019; Sigdel et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2021; Vinet et al., 2024). Unlike pro-

Table 2. Features of the posterior distribution (mean, 95% high probability density [95HPD], and probability of the correlation being different from 0 [$P\{\rho \neq 0\}$]) of within-trait correlations (ρ) between genetic level of the traits ($u_{\text{THI}}^{Y, \text{CR}}$) and slopes of response ($\text{Slp}_{\text{THI}}^{Y, \text{CR}}$) under values of the temperature-humidity index (THI) representing comfort ($\text{THI}_Y = 55$, $\text{THI}_{\text{CR}} < 66$) and heat stress ($\text{THI}_Y = 72, 77$; $\text{THI}_{\text{CR}} = 69, 74$) obtained in the bicharacter analyses considering conception rate (CR) and one of each of the productive traits (Y), milk, fat, and protein yields

ρ	Milk yield			Fat yield			Protein yield		
	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$
$\text{Slp}_{72}^Y, u_{55}^Y$	-0.58	[-0.72, -0.44]	1.00	-0.44	[-0.67, -0.21]	1.00	-0.41	[-0.57, -0.25]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{72}^Y, u_{72}^Y$	-0.38	[-0.56, -0.2]	1.00	-0.27	[-0.53, -0.02]	0.97	-0.13	[-0.32, 0.06]	0.90
$\text{Slp}_{72}^Y, u_{77}^Y$	-0.25	[-0.44, -0.05]	0.99	-0.13	[-0.41, 0.17]	0.79	0.06	[-0.14, 0.26]	0.72
$\text{Slp}_{77}^Y, u_{55}^Y$	-0.59	[-0.73, -0.42]	1.00	-0.40	[-0.63, -0.13]	1.00	-0.38	[-0.55, -0.19]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{77}^Y, u_{72}^Y$	-0.40	[-0.59, -0.21]	1.00	-0.25	[-0.53, 0.02]	0.95	-0.12	[-0.32, 0.08]	0.86
$\text{Slp}_{77}^Y, u_{77}^Y$	-0.27	[-0.47, -0.06]	1.00	-0.10	[-0.4, 0.19]	0.73	0.07	[-0.15, 0.27]	0.75
$\text{Slp}_{72}^Y, \text{Slp}_{77}^Y$	0.99	[0.99, 1.00]	1.00	0.99	[0.98, 0.99]	1.00	0.99	[0.99, 1.00]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{\text{CR}}^{\text{CR}}, u_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	0.01	[-0.23, 0.28]	0.54	-0.02	[-0.31, 0.31]	0.55	-0.03	[-0.25, 0.18]	0.62
$\text{Slp}_{\text{CR}}^{\text{CR}}, u_{69}^{\text{CR}}$	0.40	[0.19, 0.62]	1.00	0.38	[0.12, 0.65]	1.00	0.43	[0.25, 0.61]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{\text{CR}}^{\text{CR}}, u_{74}^{\text{CR}}$	0.75	[0.63, 0.86]	1.00	0.75	[0.62, 0.89]	1.00	0.79	[0.71, 0.87]	1.00

duction traits, we hypothesize that challenging conditions may enhance the expression of genetic differences in fitness-related traits such as fertility, as suggested by Brügemann et al. (2011) and Ansari-Mahyari et al. (2019). These genetic differences may influence fertility directly or through variations in body reserve mobilization to sustain reproductive function (Friggens, 2003). The presence of substantial GxE interactions for fertility traits across the THI scale has also been reported in other studies (Shi et al., 2021; Vinet et al., 2024). The stronger GxE interaction observed for fertility suggests a greater impact of HS on fertility than on production traits. There is less consensus regarding the relationship between fertility level and the rate of response to high HL. Most studies (Ravagnolo and Misztal, 2002; Bifani et al., 2016; Sigdel et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2021) have reported negative estimates, ranging from -0.18 (Ansari-Mahyari et al., 2019) to -0.98 (Shi et al., 2021). However, Vinet et al. (2024) found a near-zero correlation for Holstein cattle in France (similar to our study), whereas a moderately positive value was estimated for the Montbéliarde breed. Interestingly, Ravagnolo and Misztal (2002) observed a substantial decrease in the estimated genetic correlation between fertility level under TN conditions and slope of reaction beyond the HS threshold when shifting from a univariate fertility analysis (-0.95) to a bivariate analysis (-0.43) including both fertility and milk yield. Bivariate models incorporating fertility and production traits have been applied by Vinet et al. (2024) and in our study. Considering milk yield may help to correct selection bias for production traits while also accounting for the negative impact of high

milk production on fertility. In our dataset, analyzing CR alone yielded a genetic correlation estimate of -0.18 between fertility level and the rate of decline under HS, only slightly higher than the bivariate estimates.

Production traits, mainly protein yield, are the primary economic drivers of dairy farms (e.g., Cole and Van Raden, 2018). These traits are easier to measure and have higher heritability than fertility. Therefore, selecting animals capable of maintaining their productivity under HS is highly desirable. However, as previously mentioned, studies conducted on highly selected dairy populations have consistently found an antagonistic relationship between production levels (for milk and quality traits) and production declines under HS. Specifically, higher-producing cows tend to be less heat tolerant in terms of productivity. A high level of production is expected to increase internal heat generation (West, 2003). When combined with the rise in body temperature under HS, this leads to impaired HT. Additionally, an animal's physiological response to HS increases its energy requirements for heat dissipation through various mechanisms. The energy demand for both HS response and high production exacerbates the negative energy balance, ultimately leading to reduced productivity under HS. In this regard, low production has been identified as an adaptive strategy in breeds originating from harsh environments where animals endure prolonged periods of high HL (Berman, 2011). However, the magnitude of the negative genetic correlations between production levels and the slopes of production decline suggests that not all high-producing animals experience severe productivity losses under HS. Two possible mechanisms related to heat dissipation and

energy allocation may explain this variation, each with different implications for the cow's lifespan. First, some highly productive animals maintain their production levels under HS due to a superior ability to dissipate heat, indicating better adaptation to hot climates and overall functionality. Some studies have shown that cows classified as heat tolerant in terms of productivity (HT-P) can regulate their body temperature more effectively than heat-sensitive cows (Garner et al., 2016; Jensen et al., 2022). This enhanced functionality is further supported by the small but positive correlations (<0.3) between HT-P and fertility levels, which we have also observed and which have been reported in previous studies (Osei-Amponsah et al., 2023). Second, highly productive Holstein genotypes tend to prioritize energy allocation to milk production at the expense of body reserves and functional needs (Puillet et al., 2021), contrary to unselected local breeds, which tend to prioritize the accumulation of body reserves (Berman, 2011). If the prioritization of milk production is the case, less pronounced production declines in high-producing cows would not necessarily indicate better heat adaptation in terms of thermoregulation. Over the long term, this energy imbalance could lead to homeostatic failure, with severe consequences for the animal unless both mechanisms—heat dissipation and efficient energy mobilization—operate simultaneously. It is also important to consider that farm mitigation strategies may have allowed the highly producing genotypes to cope with high external temperatures and show only moderate production loss. Thus, identifying HT indicators beyond production loss under HS becomes essential. Such indicators would help distinguish animals that experience lower productivity losses due to superior physiological adaptation to HS from those that prioritize milk production without better ability for heat dissipation. Our hypothesis is that heat tolerance based on fertility (HT-F) may serve as a more reliable indicator of physiological adaptation to heat. Supporting this, Nanas et al. (2020) found that cows with preserved fertility under severe HS had lower cortisol and HSP70 levels than cows with poor CR, suggesting a superior ability to cope with stress from a fertility perspective.

Interestingly, our results indicate that animals with better overall fertility levels also tended to exhibit smaller slopes of productive loss under HS, suggesting a broader connection between functionality and heat adaptation. This relationship is likely partially mediated by the lower production levels of animals with superior fertility and HT. In line with this, the estimated correlations between HT based on production (HT-P) and HT based on fertility (HT-F) were moderately high (0.22 to 0.65). This suggests that HT-P is also associated with improved thermoregulation mechanisms, enabling animals to better cope with HS while maintaining both functionality

Figure 4. Posterior mean (PM; dots) and 95% high probability density intervals (bars) of the posterior distribution for the genetic correlation conception rate (CR) and yield (Y) traits under different combinations of increasing values of the temperature-humidity index (THI). The THI values for yields (THI_Y) are daily THI means averaged over the day of milk recording and the 2 previous days, whereas THI values for CR (THI_{CR}) are daily THI means averaged over the day of insemination and the 7 subsequent days. Thermoneutrality: $THI_Y = 50$, $THI_{CR} < 66$; numbers are values for THI of each type of trait.

and production. However, as previously mentioned, this relationship is at least partially influenced by the lower production levels of animals that experience smaller productivity declines under HS.

The idea that animals capable of maintaining homeostasis under harsh conditions—such as high temperatures—also exhibit overall better functionality is supported by the observed changes in the antagonistic relationship between production and fertility under TN versus HS conditions. Specifically, the negative correlation between production levels and general fertility weakened as the THI increased, possibly reflecting a decline in production as a physiological response to HS. This suggests that the negative genetic correlation between these traits may stem from an underlying mechanism related to the animal's ability to mobilize body reserves and allocate them between production and fertility by adjusting production levels accordingly. Overall, the near-zero or slightly positive correlation between fertility and production levels under HS conditions indicates that superior genotypes for milk production under HS are unlikely to experience a decline in reproductive performance. This increases the potential for improving productivity without compromising fertility in high-temperature environments.

Table 3. Features of the posterior distribution (mean, 95% high probability density [95HPD], and probability of the correlation being different from 0 [$P\{\rho \neq 0\}$]) of across-trait correlations (ρ) between genetic level of the traits ($u_{\text{THI}}^{Y, \text{CR}}$) and slopes of response ($\text{Slp}_{\text{THI}}^{Y, \text{CR}}$) under values of the temperature-humidity index (THI) representing comfort ($\text{THI}_Y = 55$, $\text{THI}_{\text{CR}} < 66$) and heat stress ($\text{THI}_Y = 72, 77$; $\text{THI}_{\text{CR}} = 69, 74$) obtained in the bicharacter analyses considering conception rate (CR) and one of each of the productive traits (Y), milk, fat, and protein

ρ	Milk			Fat			Protein		
	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$	Mean	95HPD	$P(\rho \neq 0)$
$u_{55}^Y, u_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	-0.39	[-0.49, -0.29]	1.00	-0.14	[-0.25, -0.02]	0.99	-0.12	[-0.24, -0.01]	0.98
$u_{55}^Y, \text{Slp}_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	-0.05	[-0.34, 0.18]	0.62	-0.10	[-0.42, 0.18]	0.70	0.01	[-0.21, 0.20]	0.52
$u_{<66}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{72}^Y$	0.45	[0.24, 0.62]	1.00	0.51	[0.27, 0.73]	1.00	0.34	[0.13, 0.56]	1.00
$u_{<66}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{77}^Y$	0.47	[0.26, 0.65]	1.00	0.50	[0.25, 0.74]	1.00	0.37	[0.14, 0.59]	1.00
$u_{72}^Y, \text{Slp}_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	0.18	[-0.15, 0.41]	0.86	0.09	[-0.26, 0.39]	0.73	0.27	[0.09, 0.46]	1.00
$u_{77}^Y, \text{Slp}_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	0.28	[-0.06, 0.53]	0.92	0.14	[-0.26, 0.42]	0.80	0.34	[0.16, 0.53]	1.00
$u_{69}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{72}^Y$	0.67	[0.52, 0.82]	1.00	0.61	[0.37, 0.82]	1.00	0.51	[0.29, 0.70]	1.00
$u_{69}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{77}^Y$	0.67	[0.50, 0.83]	1.00	0.55	[0.28, 0.79]	1.00	0.48	[0.24, 0.69]	1.00
$u_{74}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{72}^Y$	0.79	[0.58, 0.92]	1.00	0.59	[0.32, 0.85]	1.00	0.55	[0.32, 0.77]	1.00
$u_{74}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{77}^Y$	0.75	[0.54, 0.92]	1.00	0.49	[0.17, 0.78]	1.00	0.49	[0.22, 0.73]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{72}^Y, \text{Slp}_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	0.65	[0.39, 0.83]	1.00	0.34	[0.01, 0.70]	0.96	0.43	[0.15, 0.69]	1.00
$\text{Slp}_{77}^Y, \text{Slp}_{<66}^{\text{CR}}$	0.59	[0.31, 0.79]	1.00	0.22	[-0.17, 0.58]	0.86	0.32	[0.01, 0.61]	0.98

CONCLUSIONS

Trade-offs between production and fertility decrease under high HL, meaning that top-performing animals in terms of production do not necessarily experience a decline in fertility, and conversely, animals with high fertility potential do not necessarily have low production. Moreover, HT measured through the response of production traits to high HL is positively associated with HT measured through CR responses. Given the greater economic impact of production on farm profitability, its higher heritability, and its ease of measurement, we propose that production response under HS or the genetic value of production traits under HS should be the primary tool for improving HT in dairy farms. However, incorporating information on functional traits, such as fertility responses to HL, is also essential. This approach ensures that selected animals achieve high production levels under HS due to better physiological adaptation to hot conditions rather than solely through energy reallocation to sustain production despite environmental constraints.

NOTES

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Nonstandard abbreviations used: AI = artificial insemination; CR = conception rate; Gx E = genotype-by-environment interaction; HL = heat load; 95HPD = 95% high probability density; HS = heat stress; HT = heat tolerance; HT-F = heat tolerance measured from fertility loss under heat stress; HT-P = heat tolerance measured from productive loss under heat stress; NRR = nonreturn rate; PM = posterior mean; THI = temperature-humidity index; THI_{CR} = average of daily average of THI values on the AI date and the subsequent 7 d; THI_Y = average of daily average THI values on the test-day of recording and the 2 previous days; TN = thermoneutral.

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APPENDIX

Here we show the matrix notation for the calculation of level of traits and slopes along THI values and corresponding (co)variance and correlations for production traits and conception rate.

The overall 2-trait model for one production trait and CR in matrix notation was

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{X}\mathbf{b} + \mathbf{H}\mathbf{h} + \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{W}\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{e}, \quad [A1]$$

where \mathbf{y} contains the vectors of the productive trait and the fertility observations; \mathbf{b} , \mathbf{h} , \mathbf{a} , and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ are vectors of unknown general environmental (age at calving, DIM, and voluntary waiting period); herd-year, sire additive genetic, and permanent environmental effects, respectively; \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{H} , \mathbf{Z} , and \mathbf{W} are the corresponding incidence matrices; and \mathbf{e} is the vector of residual terms. In [A1],

$$\mathbf{y} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{y}^Y \\ \mathbf{y}^{CR} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}^Y & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{X}^{CR} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{b} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{b}^Y \\ \mathbf{b}^{CR} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{H}^Y & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{H}^{CR} \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{h} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{h}^Y \\ \mathbf{h}^{CR} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Z}^Y & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{Z}^{CR} \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\alpha} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^Y \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{CR} \end{bmatrix} \text{ with } \boldsymbol{\alpha}^Y = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0^Y \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha}_1^Y \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha}_2^Y \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{CR} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0^{CR} \\ \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{Slp}^{CR} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W}^Y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\omega}^Y \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \text{ with } \boldsymbol{\omega}^Y = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\omega}_0^Y \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_1^Y \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_2^Y \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{e} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{e}^Y \\ \mathbf{e}^{CR} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Superscript Y refers to productive (yield) traits. \mathbf{Z}^Y is a matrix where the number of rows is equal to the number of test-day records, and the number of columns contains the 3 quadratic Legendre polynomial covariates along columns (1 for the intercept and the corresponding values for the linear and quadratic terms) for each cow's sire evaluated at the THI_Y values associated with each observation. Similarly, \mathbf{Z}^{CR} is a matrix with number of rows equal to the number of cows with a CR record, and 2 columns per cow's sire, one with unity values and an-

other one with the difference between the THI_{CR} values associated with each observation and the HS threshold for fertility or a 0 if that difference is negative. \mathbf{W}^Y , similar to \mathbf{Z}^Y , contains the covariates for the quadratic Legendre polynomials evaluated at corresponding THI_Y values, but linking now the observations for yields with the regression coefficients for permanent environmental effects for each cow.

The solutions for the intercept of the additive genetic components ($\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0^Y$ and $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0^{CR}$) are the estimated values of the genetic level of the traits when THI equals its average value (which falls within the TN region in this data). These values are interpreted as values for the genetic level under TN conditions for a given trait. Notice that the additive genetic value (\mathbf{u}) of the individual's response to THI was obtained as

$$\mathbf{u}^Y = \mathbf{Z}^Y \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^Y \text{ and } \mathbf{u}^{CR} = \mathbf{Z}^{CR} \times \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{CR} \quad [A2]$$

for production and CR, respectively.

Permanent environmental effects (\mathbf{p}) for yields along THI were obtained as

$$\mathbf{p}^Y = \mathbf{W}^Y \times \boldsymbol{\omega}^Y.$$

Apart from changes in the genetic value of the trait for different values of the THI, a genetic value for HT can be obtained from the solution for the regression coefficients for each individual. For fertility, the HT-F value would be directly obtained from $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{Slp}^{CR}$. For productive traits, solutions for the linear and quadratic regression coefficients can be used to obtain slopes of the individual response curve under HS values for THI_Y , as HT-P indicators using the formula for \mathbf{u}^Y in [A2]. Slopes (Slp) at given THI_Y values were obtained from the expression

$$\text{Slp}_{\text{THI}_Y}^Y = \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}^Y \boldsymbol{\alpha}^Y}{\partial \text{THI}_Y} = \mathbf{c}'_{\text{THI}_Y} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^Y,$$

where \mathbf{c}' is a vector that contains the derivative of the Legendre polynomial covariates in \mathbf{Z}^Y with respect to THI_Y at a given THI_Y value.

The assumed (co)variance structures for \mathbf{h} , $\boldsymbol{\omega}$, \mathbf{a} , and \mathbf{e} effects in [A1] were

$$\text{var}(\mathbf{h}) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}\sigma_h^{2Y} & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{I}\sigma_h^{2CR} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\text{var}(\omega) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_o^Y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{P}_o^Y = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{\omega_o}^{2Y} & \sigma_{\omega_o, \omega_1}^Y & \sigma_{\omega_o, \omega_2}^Y \\ \sigma_{\omega_1, \omega_o}^Y & \sigma_{\omega_1}^{2Y} & \sigma_{\omega_1, \omega_2}^Y \\ \sigma_{\omega_2, \omega_o}^Y & \sigma_{\omega_2, \omega_1}^Y & \sigma_{\omega_2}^{2Y} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{I},$$

$$\text{var}(\alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0}^{2Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_1}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_2}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_0}^{Y, CR} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_{Slp}}^{Y, CR} \\ \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_0}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1}^{2Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_0}^{Y, CR} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_{Slp}}^{Y, CR} \\ \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_2, \alpha_0}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_2}^Y & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_2}^{2Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_2, \alpha_0}^{Y, CR} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_2, \alpha_{Slp}}^{Y, CR} \\ \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_0}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_1}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_2}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0}^{2CR} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_{Slp}}^{CR} \\ \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}, \alpha_0}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}, \alpha_1}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}, \alpha_2}^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}, \alpha_0}^{CR} & \mathbf{A}\sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}}^{2CR} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{G}_o^Y & \mathbf{G}_o^{Y, CR} \\ \mathbf{G}_o^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{G}_o^{CR} \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{A},$$

$$\text{var}(e) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^{2Y} & \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^{Y, CR} \\ \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^{CR, Y} & \mathbf{I}\sigma_e^{2CR} \end{bmatrix},$$

where matrices \mathbf{I} are identity matrices and matrix \mathbf{A} is the additive genetic relationship matrix for sires of cows $\mathbf{G}_o^Y = \text{var}(\alpha^Y)$, $\mathbf{G}_o^{CR} = \text{var}(\alpha^{CR})$, and $\mathbf{G}_o^{Y, CR} = \text{covar}(\alpha^Y, \alpha^{CR})$, \otimes is the Kronecker product symbol, \mathbf{P} is the matrix of (co)variances between random regression coefficients of polynomials defining the changes in cow permanent environmental effects along the thermal load scale for production traits, \mathbf{G} is the matrix of (co)variances between random regression coefficients of polynomials defining the changes in sire additive genetic effects along the thermal load scale for production and fertility traits, and the σ parameters are the (co)variance components to estimate.

From the (co)variances for genetic effects for both traits, $\mathbf{G}_o^Y, \mathbf{G}_o^{CR}, \mathbf{G}_o^{Y, CR}$, variances, and genetic correlations between genetic values along the THI scale, the general level (intercepts) and HT indicators (slopes) can be obtained as

- $\text{Var}(\mathbf{u}^Y) = \mathbf{Z}^Y \mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{Z}^{Y'}$ and $\text{Var}(\mathbf{u}^{CR}) = \mathbf{Z}^{CR} \mathbf{G}_o^{CR} \mathbf{Z}^{CR'}$ for (co)variances between genetic values along the THI_Y or THI_{CR} scale, respectively,
- $\text{Var}(\mathbf{p}^Y) = \mathbf{W}^Y \mathbf{P}_o^Y \mathbf{W}^{Y'}$, for (co)variances between permanent environmental values along the THI_Y scale.
- $$h_{\text{THI}_Y}^2 = \frac{4 \times \text{diag}(\mathbf{Z}^Y \mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{Z}^{Y'})}{\text{diag}(\mathbf{Z}^Y \mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{Z}^{Y'}) + \text{diag}(\mathbf{W}^Y \mathbf{P}_o^Y \mathbf{W}^{Y'}) + \sigma_h^2 + \sigma_e^{2Y}}$$
 for the heritability of yield traits at values in vector THI_Y .
- $$h_{\text{THI}_{CR}}^2 = \frac{4 \times \text{diag}(\mathbf{Z}^{CR} \mathbf{G}_o^{CR} \mathbf{Z}^{CR'})}{\text{diag}(\mathbf{Z}^{CR} \mathbf{G}_o^{CR} \mathbf{Z}^{CR'}) + \sigma_h^2 + \sigma_e^{2CR}}$$
 for the heritability of yield traits at values in vector THI_{CR} .
- $$\text{Cor}(u^Y, u^{CR}) = \frac{\mathbf{Z}^Y \mathbf{G}_o^{Y, CR} \mathbf{Z}^{CR'}}{\sqrt{\mathbf{Z}^Y \mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{Z}^{Y'} \times \mathbf{Z}^{CR} \mathbf{G}_o^{CR} \mathbf{Z}^{CR'}}$$
 for correlations between genetic values for a productive trait and fertility at given values in THI_Y and THI_{CR} .
- $\text{Var}(\mathbf{c}'\alpha^Y) = \mathbf{c}'\mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{c}$ for (co)variances between slopes of response for a productive trait at different values in THI_Y .
- $$\text{Cor}(\alpha_0^Y, \alpha_0^{CR}) = \frac{\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_0}^{Y, CR}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\alpha_0}^{2Y} \times \sigma_{\alpha_0}^{2CR}}}$$
 for correlation between intercepts (levels) of the 2 traits.
- $$\text{Cor}(\text{Slp}_{HS}^Y, \text{Slp}_{HS}^{CR}) = \frac{\text{cov}(\text{Slp}_{HS}^Y, \text{Slp}_{HS}^{CR})}{\sqrt{\text{var}(\text{Slp}_{HS}^Y) \times \text{var}(\text{Slp}_{HS}^{CR})}} = \frac{\mathbf{c}'\mathbf{G}_o^{Y, CR} \mathbf{c}}{\sqrt{\mathbf{c}'\mathbf{G}_o^Y \mathbf{c} \times \sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}}^{2CR}}}$$
 for correlations between slopes (tolerance) at given values in THI_Y in the HS region.
- $$\text{Cor}(\alpha_0^Y, \text{Slp}_{HS}^{CR}) = \frac{\sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_{Slp}}^{Y, CR}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\alpha_0}^{2Y} \times \sigma_{\alpha_{Slp}}^{2CR}}}$$
 for correlations between intercept (level) of the productive trait and slope (tolerance) under HS for fertility.

- $$\text{Cor}(\alpha_0^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{Y}}) = \frac{\text{cov}(\pm_0^{\text{CR}}, \mathbf{c}'\pm^{\text{Y}})}{\sqrt{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\pm_0}^{\text{CR}} \times \mathbf{c}'\mathbf{G}_o^{\text{Y}}\mathbf{c}}} = \frac{\mathbf{c}' \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\pm_0, \pm_0}^{\text{Y,CR}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\pm_1, \pm_0}^{\text{Y,CR}} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\pm_2, \pm_0}^{\text{Y,CR}} \end{bmatrix}}{\sqrt{\tilde{\mathbf{A}}_{\pm_0}^{\text{CR}} \times \mathbf{c}'\mathbf{G}_o^{\text{Y}}\mathbf{c}}}$$

for correlations between intercept (level) for fertility and slope (tolerance) for a yield trait at a given THI_Y in the HS region.

- $$\text{Cor}(u_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}}, \text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{CR}}) = \frac{\text{cov}(u_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}}, \text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{CR}})}{\sqrt{\text{var}(u_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}}) \times \text{var}(\text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{CR}})}} = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}}' \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{\alpha_0, \alpha_{\text{Slp}}}^{\text{Y,CR}} \\ \sigma_{\alpha_1, \alpha_{\text{Slp}}}^{\text{Y,CR}} \\ \sigma_{\alpha_2, \alpha_{\text{Slp}}}^{\text{Y,CR}} \end{bmatrix}}{\sqrt{\mathbf{z}_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}}' \mathbf{G}_o^{\text{Y}} \mathbf{z}_{\text{THI}_Y}^{\text{Y}} \times \sigma_{\alpha_{\text{Slp}}}^{\text{CR}}}}$$

for genetic correlations between the genetic level for a yield trait at a given value of THI_Y and the slope of response in CR under HS.

- $$\text{Cor}(u_{\text{THI}_{\text{CR}}}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{Y}}) = \frac{\text{cov}(u_{\text{THI}_{\text{CR}}}^{\text{CR}}, \text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{Y}})}{\sqrt{\text{var}(u_{\text{THI}_{\text{CR}}}^{\text{CR}}) \times \text{var}(\text{Slp}_{\text{HS}}^{\text{Y}})}} = \frac{\mathbf{z}_{\text{THI}_{\text{CR}}}^{\text{CR}}' \mathbf{G}_o^{\text{Y,CR}} \mathbf{c}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{\alpha_{\text{slp}}}^{\text{CR}} \times \mathbf{z}_{\text{HS}_Y}^{\text{Y}}' \mathbf{G}_o^{\text{Y}} \mathbf{z}_{\text{HS}_Y}^{\text{Y}}}}$$

for the genetic correlation between the genetic level for CR at a given value of THI_{CR} and the slope of response of a yield trait under HS.